

Effects of monochromatic light on the growth of *Oedogonium* species for biofuel production

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ABSTRACT

Effects of red and blue colour of monochromatic lights at intensities of 500 lux, 1000 lux, 1500 lux and 2000 lux on the growth of *Oedogonium* sp. The cell growth was monitored by measuring the optical density (absorbance) at 680 nm using a Digital Spectrophotometer. GC-MS analysis was also carried out for extraction of *Oedogonium* sp. The results showed maximum values for absorbance 0.378 Au and 0.364 Au for blue and red light respectively at 2000 lux. While minimum values of 0.237 Au and 0.249 Au were obtained at intensity of 500 lux for blue light and red light respectively. The pigment concentration showed a consistent daily increase, with a maximum pigment concentration of chlorophyll a 4.31 mg/L and chlorophyll b 7.36 mg/L for blue light and chlorophyll a 4.15 mg/L and chlorophyll b 7.09 mg/L for red light at 2000 lux. Result for GC-MS analysis produced 12 volatile components; 10 hydrocarbons and 2 acids, which implies that the major content of the algal oil are hydrocarbons. The presence of large number of hydrocarbons in the extract suggests that the algae sample is a potential source of biofuels. In effect, achieving optimum photosynthetic efficiency is necessary for industrial application of *Oedogonium* sp.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A rising population combined with an economic growth has led to a tremendous increase in the global energy demand, which is largely supplied by fossil fuel that is unsustainable, depleting and causing environmental degradation that negatively impact on aquatic life through oil spill, rise in sea levels and flooding of low lying areas. Also, their combustion lead to increase emissions of greenhouse gases (GHG) like Carbon (IV) oxide (CO₂), oxides of Sulphur (SO_x) and oxides of Nitrogen (NO_x) [1]. To eradicate or minimize the associated problems of fossil fuels, there are various ongoing research on sustainable and alternative energy sources such as biofuel. Biofuels are renewable fuels derived from recently dead or living biological materials. The term covers solid biomass such as firewood, liquid fuels such as bioethanol (gasoline-equivalent) or biodiesel (diesel-equivalent), and gaseous forms such as biogas (e.g. methane) or hydrogen [2]. In its simplest analysis, biofuels are biodegradable, renewable and regarded to be carbon neutral

because all CO₂ released during biofuel combustion is offset by carbon fixation during plant growth. When in the liquid form (bioethanol or biodiesel), can be used as a fuel for vehicles in its pure form without major modifications in engines [3]. They also have low sulfur, aromatic calorific content, high combustion efficiency and are environmentally friendly [4-5].

Despite the considerable benefits of biofuels, they are not without their tradeoffs such as direct and indirect substantial land-use change. Direct land-use change occurs when non-agricultural lands, or diverse agroforestry systems, are converted to grow biofuel crops. While, indirect land-use change occurs when the diversion of current food or feed crops (e.g., corn), or croplands (e.g. corn fields) used for producing biofuels (e.g. corn-based bioethanol) causes farmers to respond by clearing non-agricultural lands to replace the displaced crops [6-7]. There is also the problem of high demand for water; all these tradeoffs have led to more innovative research for a better fossil fuel alternative which is biofuel from microalgae.

Biofuel production from microalgae has lots of advantages over other raw materials such as crops, waste cooking oil, etc. Microalgae have short doubling time which is around 12-24 hours due to their simple structure and are capable of high photosynthetic efficiency making them produce more oil per acre than any terrestrial crops [8]. Algae can be grown on land not suitable for agricultural cultivation, as well as applied in bioremediation of polluted water from agricultural run-off and sewage treatment plants and as fertilizers fixing nitrogen. Additionally, they can be cultivated with flue gas CO₂ as carbon source and reduce global warming by sequestering atmospheric CO₂ [9].

The design of energy efficient systems for the growth of microalgae is important due to the enormous potential for algae-based products in numerous applications. The goal in any Photo-Bio-Reactor (PBRs) is to achieve optimal growth of the algal species being cultivated. One of the major factors that must be considered for the successful growth of microalgae is light. The criteria of light sources for cultivation of photosynthetic microorganism should include high electrical efficiency, low heat dissipation, reasonable compactness, reliability, long lifetime, low cost, high durability and spectral output falling within the absorption spectrum of the microalgae of interest [10]. It has been shown that light requirements for microalgal growth in photobioreactors should be adequate and appropriate in terms of duration, intensity and wavelength, such that insufficient light may lead to growth-limiting or photo-oxidation and photo-inhibition [11]. Study by Miao *et al.* [12], on the effects of light intensity and quality of three kinds of Light Emitting Diode (LED) monochromatic lights (blue, green and red) on the growth of *Skeletonema costatum* grown in batch culture conditions, showed that growth rates increased with enhanced light intensities; however, the light level beyond the saturation intensity inhibited the growth, and concluded that under different monochromatic light, the saturated light intensity decreases and the growth rate increases with the increasing of spectrum absorption coefficient. Study by Munir *et al.* [13] on *Oedogonium* sp in the laboratory using three light sources after 30 days has the following optical density (OD₆₈₀) values for direct sunlight 1.02, indirect sunlight 0.74 and fluorescence white light 0.95. The light source in their studies was white light, which is a composition of seven colours of monochromatic lights. In order to determine the role of light wavelength on the growth of *Oedogonium* sp and explain the effects of photosynthesis mechanism, it is necessary to research the effect of the monochromatic light on the growth conditions of *Oedogonium* sp.

Light is a segment of the electromagnetic radiation spectrum, sandwiched between ultraviolet and infrared radiation. The visible portion of the electromagnetic spectrum extends from about 380 to about 780 nanometers (nm).

According to Max Planck's electromagnetic theory, energy is inversely proportional to wavelength.

$$E = \frac{hc}{\lambda} \text{-----(1)}$$

Where E is energy in Joules, *h* is Planck's constant (6.626 x 10³⁴ Js), *c* is the speed of light in a vacuum (3 x 10⁸ms⁻¹) and *λ* is the wavelength of light in (m). This implies that, shorter wavelengths have higher energy, whereas longer wavelengths have lower energy per photon. However, radiation of 750 nm and above has energy content too low to initiate chemical changes; hence, radiant energy absorbed in this range will only appear as thermal effects. Conversely, (wavelengths) radiation of 380 nm and below bring about ionizing effects. Between 380 nm and 750 nm, the energy content is sufficient to produce chemical changes in the absorbing molecules, as happened throughout the photosynthetic pathways prevailing in microalgae [14]. Hence, visible light is the main source for energy for autotrophic microalgae to produce organic compounds using the photosynthetic process. In this work, the effects of two monochromatic lights of different wavelengths and different light intensities on the growth of *Oedogonium* sp was studied.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1.1 Preparation of nutrient

Bold's basal medium (BBM) was used in the cultivation of the green microalgae, due to its stimulative effect on the growth of *Oedogonium* sp. The composition of the media is as follows: CaCl₂ (25 mg/L), NaCl (25 mg/L), NaNO₃ (250 mg/L), MgSO₄ (75 mg/L), KH₂PO₄ (105 mg/L), K₂HPO₄ (75 mg/L). Into 950 ml of DH₂O, 10 ml each of the above component was added and autoclaved.

2.1.2 Trace metal solution

Into 950 ml of DH₂O, the components such as 4.36 g of Na₂EDTA.2H₂O, 3.15 g of FeCl₂.6H₂O, 1 ml of CuSO₄.5H₂O, 1 ml of ZnSO₄.7H₂O, 1 ml of CoCl₂.6H₂O, 1 ml of MnCl₂.4H₂O, 1 ml of Na₂MoO₄.2H₂O and 1.00 g of H₂BO₃ were added and brought to a final volume of 1litre with dH₂O and autoclaved.

2.1.3 Vitamins solution

Into 950 ml of DH₂O, dissolve 100 mg of Thiamine+ HCL (Vitamin B), 1ml Biotin (Vitamin H) and 1ml Cyanocobalamin (Vitamin B₁₂) bringing the final volume to 1litre with DH₂O, Filter-sterilize and store in refrigerator or freezer. The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 7.5 and then autoclaved.

2.2 *In situ* measurements at station

The Physio-Chemical parameters of the water sample at the station were carried out as follows: The depth of the water was determined using a meter rule. The temperature of the water was determined using a Mercury-in-glass thermometer. The conductivity of the water was determined using an Adwa AD31 and AD32 instrument, a professional IP67 water proof meter with values in mSm^{-1} . The conductivity was measured by inserting the probe into 200 ml of the water sample and recorded. Phillips pH meter was used to determine the pH level of the water. Three buffer solutions (pH 4.0, 7.0, 10.0) were used for calibration and standardization. A portable refractometer was used in-situ to determine the salinity of the water sample and recorded in percentage. It was ensured that the surface of the prism and cover plate were cleaned after every measurement. Air temperature was measured *in situ* at the station using Mercury-in-glass thermometer by holding the instrument above the water surface for about 2-3 minutes while the thermometer bulb was shielded from sunlight as precaution measures. The reading was recorded in $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

2.3 Laboratory experimental setup and algae cultivation

Algae sample *Oedogonium* sp. was collected from the Department of Botany, University of Lagos, Nigeria. Eight (8) 250 mL Erlenmeyer Flasks, each filled with 150 mL of BBM were used as algae growth reactors. For the illumination, blue and red colour monochromatic light of intensities 500 lux, 1000 lux, 1500 lux

and 2000 lux powered by a dc voltage source were used. The light intensity was measured using a Digital Lux Meter (MAXTECH LX-1010B). The light-dark cycle was 14-10 hours. The temperature of the chamber was maintained between 25°C and 30°C . The flasks were shaken twice daily to ensure uniform mixture of nutrients to prevent clumping of the samples, during the culture (incubation) period.

2.4 Measurement of algae growth rate and GC-MS analysis

The cell growth was monitored by measuring the transmittance and the optical density (absorbance) at 680 nm using a Digital Spectrophotometer (Unico Spectrophotometer; Model: 1200). Readings were taken at a day interval for over two weeks, the samples were measured twice and the average values were considered. The GC-MS analysis of various organic crude extracts isolated from *Oedogonium* sp was performed using a Perkin Elmer GC-MS (Model Perkin Elmer Clarus 500, USA) at the Central Laboratory in University of Lagos.

2.5 Photosynthetic pigment determination

All algae use chlorophyll a to collect photosynthetically active light. Green algae and euglenophytes also use chlorophyll b in addition to chlorophyll a. The pigment concentration (mg/L) was determined using Jeffrey *et al.* [15] equation, given as:

$$\text{Concentration of pigment (mg/L)} = \left(\frac{\text{Absorbance units (Au)}}{\text{Specific Absorption Coefficient } \left(\frac{\text{L}}{\text{g cm}} \right)} \right) \times 1000$$

Where the specific Absorption Coefficient for chlorophyll a is $87.67 \text{ Lg}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ and for chlorophyll b is $51.36 \text{ Lg}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$.

2.6 Determination of energy of blue and red photons

The visible spectrum of the monochromatic red light wavelength (λ) used was 660 nm:

$$E = \frac{hc}{\lambda}$$

$$E = \frac{6.626 \times 10^{-34} \times 3 \times 10^8}{660 \times 10^{-9} \times 1.6 \times 10^{-19}} = 1.88 \text{ eV}$$

$$8 \text{ moles} \times 6.022 \times \frac{10^{23}}{\text{mole}} \times 1.88 \text{ eV} \times 1.6 \times \frac{10^{-19}}{\text{eV}} = 1.4 \times 10^6 \text{ Joule}$$

The visible spectrum of the monochromatic blue light wavelength (λ) used was 470 nm

$$E = \frac{6.626 \times 10^{-34} \times 3 \times 10^8}{470 \times 10^{-9} \times 1.6 \times 10^{-19}} = 2.64 \text{ eV}$$

$$8 \text{ moles} \times 6.022 \times \frac{10^{23}}{\text{mole}} \times 2.64 \text{ eV} \times 1.6 \times \frac{10^{-19}}{\text{eV}} = 2.0 \times 10^6 \text{ Joule}$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of the physio-chemical parameters taken from the water sample in Table 1 shows

that the freshwater is slightly acidic and highly conductive. The water body is very shallow and with moderate temperature. The shallowness allowed light to penetrate easily to the bottom of

the culture and evenly distributed, while the moderate temperature is to avoid overheating, which inhibits algae growth. According to Raghavan *et al.* [16], salinity of 25 % and 35 % had no significant effect on growth, maximum cell density, biomass and chlorophyll content of *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumilus*, although a tendency of higher growth, biomass and lower cell density was observed at lower salinity. Hirata *et al.* [17] observed that growth of *Chlorella saccharophila* linearly decreased with increasing salinities from 40 to 60 %. Renaud *et*

al. [18] attributed the higher growth rate of *Chaetoceros sp.* to an increase in temperature from 25 to 30°C. Buck and Smith [19] and Burja *et al.* [20] suggested that algae can adapt to variable pH conditions. Whereas Thornton [21] reported that photosynthetic efficiency of some algae decreases as the environment surrounding the cells becomes more acidic. Thus, physio-chemical parameters under which the cultivation was carried is an ideal condition that do not have negative effect on the growth rate as stated from other studies.

Table 1. Result of Physio-Chemical parameters of the water sample.

S/N	Parameters	Values
1	pH	6.6
2	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	52.6
3	Salinity (ppt)	25%
4	Air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	27
5	Surface temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	25
6	Depth (cm)	0.2

3.1 Effects of light on the growth of *Oedogonium* species

Light absorption occurs when molecules take up the energy of a photon of light, thereby reducing the transmission of light as it is passed through a sample. For a clear solution, light attenuates exponentially as it passes through. Therefore, a high absorbance is expected when a beam of light encounters a solution for a long period of time, while for a short period of time a low absorbance is expected. A lot of studies and experimental work have been done on the effect of light intensity and spectral quality of monochromatic light on different types of microalgae photosynthesis, most of these studies were conducted over a very short photoperiod of between 30 seconds and 7 days [22]. To the best of our knowledge, there is virtually no published work on the effect of different colours monochromatic light on *Oedogonium* species. Yusuf and Yan [23] reported that selection of viable microalgae is a challenge to large-scale production, since algae

has different species, and not all these species have the growth capability to be used for biofuel in commercial scale. This work was conducted for seventeen days and a photoperiod of 14-10 hours to determine the most suitable wavelength for photosynthetic rate in *Oedogonium* species, and also to study the prospects and growth capability. Firstly, we studied the effect of blue light on the growth rate of *Oedogonium sp.* For all light intensities, there was no lag phase, it was linear till the end of the culture period. Though, the growth rate was significantly different for different light intensities. This effect was observed based on the absorbance values recorded at 680 nm spectrophotometer measurement. Fig.1 shows that the absorbance increases with increase in light intensity, depicting an increase in growth rate. The maximum value achieved in the entire cultivation period was 0.378 absorbance unit (Au) at 2000 lux. While the minimum values achieved for the same period was 0.237 Au at 500 lux.

Figure 1. Effect of blue wavelength on the growth of *Oedogonium sp.*

An increase in the growth rate of microalgae with light intensity under red light was also observed, with a maximum value of 0.364 Au at 2000 lux and a minimum value of 0.249 Au at 500 lux. The effect of the red light on the growth of the *Oedogonium* sp. was obvious as no

adaptation phase was observed, the algae growth increased almost linearly with time at increasing light intensity. The growth response as a function of intensity for *Oedogonium* sp. is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Effect of red wavelength on the growth of *Oedogonium* sp.

Previous studies have shown that red and blue lights are capable of inducing photosynthesis even at low levels of exposure. Shugarman and Appleman [24] reported that inoculation at low light intensity reduces the duration of lag phase, and subsequently increases chlorophyll synthesis and growth rate of microorganism. Also, microalgae perform photosynthesis at a high efficiency under low light conditions. However, under bright sunlight, it is difficult to achieve a high photosynthetic efficiency, because cells absorb more light energy than can be converted to biochemical energy. Consequently, microalgae dissipate part of the absorbed light energy as heat which inhibit the growth rate [25]. At the early days of cultivation, the red light showed better growth rates than the blue lights until after the fifth day, when the growth rate under blue light outgrows that of red light. This implies that the acclimatization period of algae under red light is faster than that of blue light. The reason while the blue light was able to overtake the red light in growth rate is based on the Max Planck's energy expression in equation (1); energy is inversely proportional to wavelength. The wavelength of blue laser light is 470 nm, while red laser light has a wavelength of 660 nm. In effect, the photon of blue light has more energy than photon of red light hence, blue photon was reported to produce a better algae growth than the red photon at the end of the cultivation.

The growth rates for blue light at all intensities are approximately linear as shown in Fig.1. The high determination coefficient (R^2) values show that the growth rate adheres strongly to the linear function, signifying the growth trend to be linear during the cultivation period. However, this was not so with red light, where only light

intensities of 1500 lux and 2000 lux show linear relationships. For blue light the best linear relationship; $R^2 = 0.9874$ was achieved at 1500 lux, while the best linear relationship under red light; $R^2 = 0.9440$ was attained at 2000 lux. Results from previous study of *Oedogonium* sp. using natural light gave better maximum biomass concentration at the end of cultivation. However, at low intensity of light the blue and red wavelengths are capable of inducing photosynthesis, and also have a shorter lag phase which is very important, so as to have a prolonged exponential phase. The study by Munir *et al.* [13] *Oedogonium* sp. in the laboratory using three light sources after 30days measured the optical density to be direct sunlight 1.02, indirect sunlight 0.74 and fluorescence white light 0.95. In this study the maximum optical density obtained after 17 days was 0.378 and 0.364 for blue and red light respectively at 2000lux. While minimum values of 0.237 and 0.249 were obtained at intensity of 500lux for blue light and red light respectively. Though, the values obtained by Munir *et al.* [13] was higher. However, growth rate increases with increasing light intensity, thus, if the intensity of blue and red light is increased further up to optimal light intensity which according to Simionato *et al.*, (2013) is between 1000-10,000 lux, the result could be better than that of Munir *et al.* [13].

3.2 Concentration of photosynthetic pigment

The results according to Jeffrey *et al.* [15] equation, under blue light cultivation the calculated concentration of photosynthetic pigment has maximum pigment concentrations of chlorophyll a 4.31 mg/L and chlorophyll b 7.36 mg/L at light intensity of 2000 lux. And the

minimum pigment concentrations were chlorophyll a 2.70 mg/L and chlorophyll b 4.61mg/L at intensity of 500 lux under blue light as shown in Figures 3 and 4. The results in figures (3 to 6) show that pigment concentration increases consistently on daily basis. On days 3 and 5, pigment concentration was higher at 1500 lux. Then on day 7, there was a sudden increase in the pigment concentration at 2000 lux from 1.69 mg/L to 2.49 mg/L. Higher values

at 1500 lux were later observed on day 11 and 13, and then, on days 15 and 17, the pigment values observed were higher at 2000 lux. The reason for this is that, chlorophyll concentration in the algal cell varies according to the amount of light available. More so, blue light is both high in energy and strongly absorbed by chlorophyll, which can be used effectively in photosynthesis. Thus, at high intensity there is increase in photosynthetic efficiency.

Figure 3. Effect of blue wavelength on chlorophyll a concentration.

Figure 4. Effect of blue wavelength on chlorophyll b concentration.

Red light is also strongly absorbed by algae, hence, under red light cultivation maximum pigment concentrations of chlorophyll a 4.15 mg/L and chlorophyll b 7.09 mg/L were obtained at light intensity of 2000 lux, while minimum pigment concentrations of chlorophyll a 2.84 mg/L and chlorophyll b 4.84 mg/L were obtained

for light intensity at 500 lux for the period of cultivation, as shown in Figures 5 and 6. Sudden increase in pigment on days 5 and 17 for 2000 lux, and day 15 for 1500 lux was observed. This implies an increase in photosynthetic efficiency.

Figure 5. Effect of red wavelength on chlorophyll a concentration.

Figure 6. Effect of red wavelength on chlorophyll b concentration.

The primary photosynthetic pigments of *Oedogonium* sp. chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b determine which wavelengths of light are utilized in photosynthesis. Pigments form aggregates on the thylakoid membrane called photosystems [26]. The purpose of these photosystems is to collect energy over a broad range of wavelengths and concentrate it to one molecule called a reaction center which uses the energy to pass one of its electrons on to a series of enzymes [26-27]. Accordingly, there are two kinds of Photosystems in most photosynthetic eukaryotes, which are photosystem I (PS I) and photosystem II (PS II). Photosystem I consist largely of chlorophyll a molecules and contains no or few chlorophyll b. It absorbs light of 700 nm maximally. Photosystem II contains chlorophyll a, as well as up to 50% chlorophyll b. It is needed to capture enough energy to do the biosynthetic reactions

of the dark reaction and absorbs light maximally at 680 nm. When PS I & II work together, they absorb enough energy from light source to split a molecule of water [26-28]. The better growth rate in blue light than in red was probably due to higher photosynthetic efficiency and quantum yield in the blue light. The increase in photosynthetic efficiency in blue light could be attributed to an acclimation in low irradiance and because the spectrum of the blue-light field used supplied adequate photons to both PSI & II was optimal for photosynthesis. Thus, stimulating the accumulation of pigments that efficiently absorb the broad-band blue light applied. For the red-light field PSI was supplied with enough photons to stimulate photosynthesis, but the photons supplied to PS II was inadequate. A study by Figueroa *et al* (1994) reported that, the light absorption around the maximal transmission of the blue light used

(440- 480 nm) was 1.2-1.5 times smaller than that around the maximal transmission of the red light used (630-670 nm).

3.3 Energy of blue and red photon

The three stages of photosynthesis involve firstly, capturing energy from light source. Secondly, using the energy to make Adenosine (T) triphosphate (ATP) and reducing

nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate NADP^+ (an electron carrier molecule) to Nicotinamide Adenine Dinucleotide Phosphate Oxidase (NADPH) and thirdly, which is the Calvin cycle, uses the ATP and NADPH to reduce the carbon in carbon dioxide and form a simple sugar whose carbon skeleton can be used to synthesize other organic molecules (carbon fixation) [29].

The energy derived from light absorption is used in particular pathways to achieve the final result of synthesis of sugars. Since the pathways are known, a theoretical maximum efficiency can be calculated. It is known that a total of 8 photons of light must be absorbed to reduce two molecules of NADP^+ . Operating in the Calvin cycle, the resulting two molecules of NADPH can produce one hexose molecule. Using Max Planck's energy equation, the energy of photon of red light (660 nm) is 1.88 eV and blue light (470 nm) is 2.64 eV. For 8 moles of such photons the energy absorbed in Joules for red photon is 1.4×10^6 J, while for blue photon is 2.0×10^6 J. It takes 0.5×10^6 J to reduce one mole of CO_2 to hexose, so the theoretical efficiency for red photon is 33%, and blue photon is 23%. This means that 33% of photon energy from red light and 23% of photon energy

from blue light are needed to convert the same amount of mole of CO_2 to simple sugar. The energy absorb by microalgae from red and blue light is useful for sequestration of atmospheric CO_2 .

3.4 GC-MS analysis

Hexane extract method was employed in the GC-MS analysis on *Oedogonium* sp. Hexane was used because it is a non-polar solvent, high stability, low greasy residual effects, boiling point and low corrosiveness. Figures 7 shows the percentage compositions and nature of the compounds extracted. Aliphatic hydrocarbon 31.81% is the dominant compound, while phenol 6.6% is the least compound. The total percentage of the hydrocarbon composition is 86.74% and the organic acid is 13.26%.

Figure 7. Composition of Volatile oils of *Oedogonium* sp. (GC-MS analysis).

The total number of volatile components produced was twelve; ten hydrocarbons and two acids. The hydrocarbons include 1-docosene, butylated hydroxytoluene, nonadecane, 1-nonadecene, eicosane, tricosane and heneicosane. The acid was nonahexacontanoic acid. Products such as cosmetics and soap additives can be produced from the organic

acid. While, biofuels such as biodiesel, jetfuel; lubricant and wax can be produced from the hydrocarbons. Figure 8 below shows the name and quality of the compound of hydrocarbons produced. This result shows that, the dominant constituent of *Oedogonium* sp. are hydrocarbons.

Figure 8. Volatile components from the crude extract of *Oedogonium sp* having minimum quality ≥ 90 .

Figure 9. GC–MS analysis of composition of the volatile hydrocarbons in *Oedogonium sp*.

The GC–MS analysis of composition of the volatile hydrocarbons in *Oedogonium sp*. in Figure 9 shows the potential of *oedogonium sp*. as a source of biofuels as seen in large number (10) and quality (above 90) of hydrocarbons extracted. This study is in agreement with Adesalu *et al.* [30]. Also, comparing the result of this present study with that of Hossain [31] revealed that hexane extract of *Oedogonium* and *Spirogyra sp.*, *Oedogonium* yielded more volatile components (methyl ester) than *Spirogyra* which was useful in biofuel production. Hence, this is an indication that extraction with different solvents (polar and non-polar) and method of extraction could affect the yield of different bioactive compounds from algae. The potential of the lipid content of

Oedogonium sp. from this study may be affected by the hot method of extraction used for crude extract. Thus, the study of volatile components of various microalgae is necessary for consideration as source of alternative energy.

4. CONCLUSION

To the best of our knowledge, there is virtually no published work on the effect of different colours monochromatic light on *Oedogonium* species. This study has shown that light wavelength has a noticeable effect on the algal growth rates. Thus, using monochromatic blue and red light at appropriate light intensity of 2000 lux significantly enhance the growth rate of

Oedogonium sp. However, the growth rate under blue light produced a better result than red. Also, the blue light has a greater photosynthetic efficiency than the red light as depicted by the result of the pigment concentration of chlorophyll a and b. Furthermore, *Oedogonium* sp. has the potential to become an alternative fuel source due to the amount of hydrocarbon compounds it contains. For large scale algal growth, the light intensity should be increased but not beyond the optimum light intensity level.

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